

A Review of Analytical Methods on Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone

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ABSTRACT

Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone both are oral hypoglycaemic agents. Both the agents are used in the treatment of diabetes mellitus type 2. Dapagliflozin is sodium glucose co-transporter 2 (SGL2) inhibitor. It was approved for treatment of T2DM in the European Union in November 2012. Lobeglitazone works by activating peroxisome proliferator activated receptor gamma (PPAR gamma). It was created in South Korea. This paper discuss various published analytical methods described in literature for estimation of Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone in various pharmaceutical formulations and biological sample. It includes different techniques like UV spectrophotometry, high performance liquid chromatography, high performance thin layer chromatography, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry. This review reveals a major gap: no analytical method has yet been published for the simultaneous estimation of the combination of dapagliflozin and lobeglitazone, despite the fact that many methods exist for the medications either alone or in combination with other agents like metformin. These results emphasize the necessity of further methodological advancements to facilitate pharmacokinetic research and quality control for this particular medicinal combination.

Keywords: DPZ= Dapagliflozin, LGZ=Lobeglitazone, Analytical methods, Diabetes mellitus type 2

INTRODUCTION

Dapagliflozin

The active moiety of Dapagliflozin (DPZ) (2S,3R,4R,5S,6R)-2-[4-chloro-3-(4-ethoxybenzyl)phenyl]-6-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydro-2H-pyran-3,4,5-triol) is sodium glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitor.^[1]Dapagliflozin is a highly selective reversible inhibitor of SGLT2 being developed for the treatment of T2DM. Data pooled across 12 Phase III clinical trials have shown Dapagliflozin to have an acceptable safety profile. Dapagliflozin was approved for the treatment of T2DM in the European Union in November 2012. This review summarizes the clinical pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of Dapagliflozin.^[1] Dapagliflozin competitively, reversibly, and highly selectively inhibits SGLT2. Type 2 SGLT2s

are expressed in the kidney and on the epithelial lining of the S1 segment of the proximal convoluted tubule. Physiologically, these transporters handle approximately 90% of renal glucose absorption. By blocking SGLT2 with Dapagliflozin, reabsorption of glucose into the bloodstream is diminished. Dapagliflozin promotes glucose filtration through the kidneys and into the urine to be eliminated from the body.^[2] Sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors are new glucose-lowering drugs with a novel insulin-independent mechanism with favourable glucose lowering effect ts. Moreover, marked benefits on cardiovascular-renal outcomes in patients with T2DM prompted an update to relevant guidelines.^[6,7] DPZ, sold under the brand names Farxiga (US) and Forxiga (EU) among others, is a medication used to treat type 2 diabetes. Chemical formula of Dapagliflozin is C₂₁H₂₅ClO₆·C₃H₈O₂·H₂O. (Mol.wt:502.98 g/mol). DPZ propanediol

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monohydrate appears as white colour non hygroscopic crystalline powder. It is soluble in ethanol, acetonitrile, slightly soluble in water and practically insoluble in hexane. [78]

Lobeglitazone:

Lobeglitazone is a pharmacophore which has a 2, 4-thiazolidinedione group with an ethoxy-benzyl N-methyl amino group bound to this as a connecting link. Its structural formula is C₂₄H₂₄N₄O₅S. Its synonyms include Duvie (Korea) and LOBG (India). The IUPAC 5-[4-(2-{{6-(4-Methoxyphenoxy)-pyrimidin-4-yl]-methyl-amino}-ethoxy)-benzyl]-thiazolidine-2,4-dione hydrosulphuricacid. Its molecular weight is 480.5 g/mol. [5,6]

Lobeglitazone was based on modification of the rosiglitazone structure to introduce a p-methoxyphenoxy group at the 4-position of the pyrimidine moiety. This contributes to enhanced binding affinity of Lobeglitazone for PPAR γ , with docking analysis suggesting that the binding affinity of Lobeglitazone is 12 times higher than that of rosiglitazone and pioglitazone. [5]

According to earlier research, Lobeglitazone medication improved lipid profiles by an 8% rise from baseline high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) levels and a 13% reduction from baseline triglycerides levels. Both as a monotherapy and in combination with metformin, Lobeglitazone was well tolerated. Because of its greater affinity for PPAR, Lobeglitazone exhibits comparable glycaemic

efficiency to pioglitazone at a lower effective dose of 0.5 mg. It is predicted that Lobeglitazone can be administered in individuals with renal insufficiency without dose reduction since it is mostly metabolized by the liver, with minor renal excretion and because it may have a lower risk of bladder cancer than other thiazolidinediones. Due to its favourable safety profile and proven ability to decrease blood sugar levels in both clinical and experimental studies, Korea has approved Lobeglitazone as an oral diabetes medication since July 2013. According to research conducted on animals, Lobeglitazone administration greatly decreased insulin resistance and enhanced the expression of GLUT4 and PPARs in mice given a high-fat diet (HFD). The prevalence of diabetes is significantly rising globally, primarily as a result of rising obesity and insulin resistance rates as well as an aging population that has an impact on mortality and quality of life. [6]

With an IC₅₀ of 20 and 18 nm, respectively, Lobeglitazone sulfate is a thiazolidinedione that works by activating PPAR- α/γ dual agonist. It was created in Korea by Chong Kun Dang Pharmaceutical to treat diabetes, and it differs significantly from the other two PPAR agonists, pioglitazone and rosiglitazone, in that it has PPAR- α activity. In South Korea and India, the medication is authorized for the management of T2DM. In a 24-week randomized, double-blind, multicenter clinical trial, Lobeglitazone sulfate 0.5 mg once daily was found to be safe and effective when compared to a placebo in treating naïve Korean people with T2D. [8]

Fig. 1 Dapagliflozin

Fig2 Lobeglitazone

Fig. 3 Overview of analytical methods for estimation of Dapagliflozin in biological and pharmaceutical sample

Fig. 4 Overview of analytical methods for estimation of Lobeglitazone in biological and pharmaceutical samples.

2. SAMPLE PREPARATION

2.1 Solubility

According to European Medicines Agency (EMA), the classification of Dapagliflozin (DPZ) falls under BCS class III, meaning it has high solubility and low permeability^[4]. It is a white crystalline powder which is soluble in ethanol, methanol, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and dimethyl formamide (DMF)^[7]. Dapagliflozin is practically insoluble in toluene and n-hexane^[7]. The Solubility chart is shown in Fig. 5.

Lobeglitazone sulfate, on the other hand, is categorized under BCS Class II, owing to its low solubility and high permeability^[5]. The Solubility chart is shown in Fig. 6. Lobeglitazone sulfate exhibits solubility in methanol and DMSO, with limited solubility in acetone^[9].

2.2 Sample preparation strategies

Sample preparation is an integral part of analytical methodology, and a variety of techniques have been reported for both Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone.

Dapagliflozin: The sample preparation techniques for the extraction of Dapagliflozin from plasma include protein precipitation with chilled acetonitrile, providing clear supernatant suitable for analysis^[151]. Alternatively, liquid–liquid extraction from human plasma allows efficient separation of the analyte from biological matrices for quantification^[70].

Lobeglitazone: The sample preparation techniques for the extraction of Lobeglitazone from biological matrices include protein precipitation using acetonitrile–methanol–water (6:3:1, v/v), yielding clear supernatant with symmetrical peaks in human plasma^[10].

Fig. 5 Solubility chart of Dapagliflozin

Fig. 6 Solubility chart of Lobeglitazone

3. ANALYTICAL METHOD

3.1 UV spectrophotometry

The UV spectrophotometric analysis of Dapagliflozin and its combinations was carried out to determine the λ_{\max} in various solvents by using different methods. The λ_{\max} values observed in the range of 203-290 nm, based on the solvent and analytical approach applied [11-39]. For example, Dapagliflozin showed λ_{\max} at 224 nm and 276 nm in methanol, 223 nm in 0.1 N HCL [15].

The methods used were simultaneous equation method, calibration curve approach, derivative ratio spectrum method, and double-beam spectrophotometry. The highest λ_{\max} was observed at 290.6 nm using the second derivative zero-crossing method [23]. Among different solvents used, methanol and water was the mostly used medium because of its excellent solubilizing capacity and reproducibility. Regarding analytical approaches, the UV

spectrophotometric method, particularly in double beam configuration, was the most commonly used technique for routine estimation, ensuring accuracy, sensitivity, and simplicity in quantitative analysis.

Analytical methods for determination of Dapagliflozin using UV spectrophotometry [11-39] are shown in Table 1.

The UV spectrophotometric analysis of Lobeglitazone and its combinations was carried out using various solvents and analytical approaches. The λ_{\max} for Lobeglitazone sulfate were reported at 350 nm in methanol, while second-order derivative spectrophotometry indicated a zero-crossing point for glimepiride at 297 nm. Methanol was the most commonly used solvent. Another determinations applied, UV-visible spectroscopy with an λ_{\max} of 252 nm in n-butanol [41], and another UV-visible spectrophotometric method showed λ_{\max} at 248 nm in methanol with high sensitivity (LOD 0.07 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) [42]. The simultaneous estimation of Lobeglitazone

with glimepiride, λ_{\max} values of 250 nm of Lobeglitazone and 227 nm of Glimepiride were used by employing Vierordt's and derivative methods [45]. These results highlight the flexibility of UV spectrophotometry in estimating Lobeglitazone

across different solvent systems and analytical methodologies. Analytical methods for determination of Lobeglitazone using UV spectrophotometry [40-47] are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Representative spectrophotometric methods for the analysis of Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone

Sr.No	Drug	Methods	λ_{\max} (nm)	Solvent/ Procedure	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Reference
1	DPZ, SGT, MTH	Simultaneous Equation Method Derivative Ratio Spectrum Zero Crossing Method	223, 212, 232.6 286.4, 219, 228.6	Water	0.0244, 0.0829, 0.0438 0.1281, 0.1185, 0.0441	[11]
2	DPZ	UV Spectrophotometric Method	224, 276	Methanol	1.2	[12]
3	DPZ	UV Spectroscopy	278	Ethanol	0.018	[13]
4	DPZ	UV Spectrophotometric Method	224	Plasma	1.09743	[14]
5	DGZ, Omer-20mg	Calibration Curve	223	0.1 N HCL	1.45	[15]
6	DPZ DPZ, MET DPZ DPZ, SAXA DPZ	Double Beam	224 230, 270 203 223, 212 233.65	Methanol Methanol Methanol Water: Methanol (80:20) Methanol	0.123	[16]
7	DPZ, TEN	Simultaneous Equation Method Q- Absorbance Ratio First Derivative (Zero Crossing)	223, 243 223, 230 243, 230 256, 243	Methanol	-	[17]
8	DPZ	Secondary Clinical Trial (DEFINE- HF) measuring ApoM& NT- probBNP	-	Plasma samples analysed by ELISA and Roche Elecsys	-	[18]
9	DPZ	UV Spectrophotometric Method	233.65	1:1 Ethanol Phosphate Buffer (pH 7.2)	1.24	[19]
10	DPZ Propane diol Monohy	UV Visible Spectrophotometry	224 276 223	Distilled Water Phosphate Buffer pH	0.1375	[20]

	drate DPZ, SAXA DPZ, TEN			6.8 Distilled Water		
11	DPZ, MET	First Derivative Spectroscopic Method	235, 272	Methanol	0.009, 0.013	[21]
12	DPZ, VGT	JV- Vis Spectrophotometry (Stability- Indicating)	200- 400	0.1 N NaOH	0.4244, 1.2352	[22]
13	DPZ, VGT	Simultaneous Equation Method (SEM) Absorbance Ratio Method (ARM) Second Derivative Zero Crossing (2DR) Ratio Difference Method (RMD) First Derivative Of Ratio Spectra (FDR)	223, 210 223, 219.2 290.6, 219.2 236,208.4 226, 215.6	Water	0.0422, 0.958 0.0422, 0.593 0.0861, 0.4407 0.0273, 0.5066 0.1404, 0.623	[23]
14	DPZ	UV Visible Spectrophotometry	220	Methanol: Water(15:85)	0.623	[24]
15	DPZ, MET	Simultaneous Equation Method (SEM)	225, 237	Methanol	-	[25]
16	DPZ	Zero Order Area Under Curve First Derivative Second Derivative	224 218-230 220 224, 235.5	Methanol, Distilled Water	-	[26]
17	DPZ, SGT	UV Spectrophotometric Method	274, 224 276, 222	Methanol: Water Phosphate Buffer PH 6.8	0.123, 0.040	[27]
18	DPZ, MTH	Simultaneous Equation Method	222, 232	Methanol, Water	0.0241, 0.0732	[28]
19	DPZ, SGT, MTH	Simultaneous Equation Method	224, 267, 233	Methanol, Distilled water	-	[29]
20	DPZ	UV Visible Spectrophotometry	224	Methanol	0.05	[30]
21	DPZ, SAXA	Simultaneous Equation Method	210, 224	Methanol	-	[31]
22	DPZ	UV Spectrophotometric Method	233.65	Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer (1:1) pH 7.2	-	[32]
23	DPZ, MET	Simultaneous Equation Method	222, 232	Methanol	0.0241, 0.0732	[33]

24	DPZ	UV Spectroscopy	224	Methanol: Water(50:50)	0.1	[34]
25	DPZ	UV Visible Spectrophotometry	237	Ethanol + Distilled water	0.0925	[35]
26	DPZ, MET	Q Absorption Ratio Method	222, 232	Water	0.0241, 0.0293	[36]
27	DPZ, SAXA	UV Visible Spectrophotometry	274, 224	Methanol: Water(40:60)	0.123, 0.040	[37]
28	DPZ	UV Visible Spectrophotometry	278	Ethanol	0.3687	[38]
29	DPZ Propane diol Monohydrate DPZ Propane diol Monohydrate (with or without MET)	Zero Spectrophotometry (ZS) First Derivative Spectrophotometry (1DS)	223.5 233	Methanol, 0.1 N HCL Methanol, Water	0.569 0.732	[39]
30	LGZ	Simultaneous Equation (Method 1) Second Order Derivative (Method 2)	250 297	Methanol	-	[40]
31	LGZ	UV-Visible Spectroscopy	252	n-Butanol	0.231	[41]
32	LGZ	UV-Visible Spectrophotometric Method	248	Methanol	0.07	[42]
33	LGZ+ Glimepiride	Simultaneous Estimation (Vierordt's & Derivative)	250, 227 2nd derivative: 297nm (Lobe)	Methanol	-	[43]
34	LGZ+ Glimepiride	Tandem UV Method	350, 226	Methanol	-	[44]
35	LGZ+ Glimepiride	Vierordt's & Q-Absorption Method	251, 228	0.1N NaOH	-	[45]
36	LGZ+ Glimepiride	First Order Derivative	226, 241	Methanol	0.066, 0.132	[46]
37	LGZ+ DPZ	Area Under Curve Method	233-243, 220-230	Methanol	0.0129, 0.4334	[47]

3.2 HPLC

The HPLC analytical methods for Dapagliflozin was carried out to reversed-phase C18 column due to its robustness and wide applicability for drug analysis. The mobile phase most frequently consisted of acetonitrile and water or buffer mixtures, often adjusted with pH modifiers such as formic acid or phosphate buffer to improve resolution [58]. UV detection was the most common detection mode, with the highest frequency of use observed at an absorbance maximum of 225-285nm.^[77] which corresponds to the strong chromophoric response of the analyte. The flow rate was usually maintained around 1.0 mL/min ^[84-86] providing optimal separation

efficiency. Analytical methods for determination of Dapagliflozin using HPLC^[48-96] are shown in Table 2.

The HPLC analytical methods for Lobeglitazone, the highest absorbance (λ_{max}) was observed at 290 nm ^[98] indicating strong UV sensitivity at this wavelength. Among the various chromatographic conditions, the most frequently employed mobile phase was a mixture of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0), methanol, acetonitrile which provided good peak resolution and reproducibility. The most commonly used column was the Phenomenex Strong Cation Exchange (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) ^[103]. Analytical methods for determination of Lobeglitazone using HPLC ^[97-107] are shown in Table

Table 2: Respective HPLC methods for the analysis of Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazon

Sr. No.	Drug	Matrix	Sample preparation	Mobile phase	Column	Detection	λ_{max} (nm)	Flow rate (ml/min)	LOD (μ g/ml)	LOQ (μ g/ml)	Ref.
1	DPZ	API and dosage form	API: 10 mg in 10 mL acetonitrile → dilute to 500 μ g/mL; Tablet: Powdered tablets equivalent to 10 mg → dissolved, sonicated, diluted to 500 μ g/mL	Acetonitrile: Dipotassium Hydrogen phosphate buffer (pH:6.5, adjusted within OPA) 40:60% v/v ratio	Agilent C18(4.6m m×150m m, 5 μ m)	Photo diode Array (PDA) Detector	222	1	5.14	15.6	[48]
2	DPZ	Raw API and Tablet Formulation	Raw drug: 1 mg dissolved in 100 mL mobile phase, sonicated, diluted to 5–25 μ g/mL range. Tablets: 10 tablets powdered, quantity	Methanol : Water (75:25 v/v)	Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ m, 95 Å)	UV detector	230	1	2.5	10.00	[49]

			equivalent to 100 mg drug dissolved in 25 mL mobile phase, filtered and diluted.								
3	DPZ+ SAXA	Bulk drug and tablet dosage form (Qtern® 10 mg/5 mg DAP/SAX tablets)	Tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg DAP + 5 mg SAX dissolved in 10 mL of diluent (acetonitrile:water 60:40), sonicated and filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filter	Acetonitrile : Water (60:40, v/v)	Xterra RP18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	248	1	3, 3.02	9.98, 10.00	[50]
4	DPZ+ SAXA	Plasma and tablet dosage form	Tablets: Powdered, dissolved in mobile phase, sonicated, filtered, diluted. Plasma: Spiked with drugs, extracted with acetonitrile, centrifuged, dried, reconstituted in mobile phase.	0.025 M Phosphate buffer (pH 4, adjusted with OPA): Acetonitrile (50:50 v/v)	XTerra C18, 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm particle size	UV detection	225	1	0.15, 0.72	0.51, 2.40	[51]

5	DPZ	Rat plasma	Liquid-liquid extraction using ethyl acetate after protein precipitation with 2% formic acid	Acetonitrile : Water (50:50 v/v)	C18 column, 250 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 µm particle size	UV detector	235	0.5	2.15 ng/ml	6.52 ng/ml	[52]
6	DPZ+MET	Bulk drug and synthetic mixture	Direct dissolution in methanol followed by dilution	Acetonitrile : Water (75:25 v/v)	Phenomenex Luna C18, 4.6 mm × 250 mm, 5 µm	PDA (photodiode array) detector	285	1	3.7, 5.0	11.4, 15.2	[53]
7	DPZ	Bulk drug and marketed tablet formulation	10 mg drug dissolved in methanol → serial dilutions to 1000 → 100 → 10 µg/mL, filtered (0.45 µm)	Methanol : Water (85:15 v/v)	Sunsil C18 column (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	225	1	0.011	0.034	[54]
8	DPZ+MET	Pharmaceutical tablet formulation	Powdered tablets dissolved in diluent (ACN:buffer), sonicated, filtered	Acetonitrile : 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid buffer (70:30 v/v), pH adjusted to 3.0	Inspire ODS C18 (4.6 × 150 mm, 5 µm)	UV/PDA	260	1	2.98, 3.05	9.95, 10.07	[55]
9	DPZ+MET HCL	Bulk and tablet formulation	Dissolution in water, sonication, dilution with water	Water : Methanol (50:50 v/v)	Phenomenex C18, 250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm	UV detection	230	1	345,000 ppb, 263,000 ppb	415,000 ppb, 324,000 ppb	[56]
10	DPZ	Bulk API and tablet dosage form	Bulk/API: 10 mg DPZgliflozin dissolved in methanol (1000 µg/mL), diluted. Tablet: Powdered,	Acetonitrile : Water (65:35 v/v)	Phenomenex Luna® LC C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	225, 278	1	0.31	0.93	[57]

			equivalent to 1 mg DPZgliflozin weighed, dissolved in methanol (100 µg/mL).								
11	DPZ + SAXA	Bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form (tablet)	Tablet powder dissolved in suitable solvent, sonicated, filtered (0.45 µm)	Phosphate buffer (pH 4) : Acetonitrile = 50:50 (v/v)	XTerra C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	225	1	1.94, 1.63	6.50, 5.39	[58]
12	DPZ + MET + Saxa	Bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form (QTE RNM ET XR tablet)	Tablet powder equivalent to label claim dissolved in diluent, sonicated, filtered, and diluted to desired concentrations : MET: 500 µg/mL DAP: 5 µg/mL SAX: 2.5 µg/mL	0.1% Ortho-phosphoric acid buffer (pH 3.0): Acetonitrile in 60:40 v/v	Kromasil C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	PDA Detector	230	1	0.003, 0.002, 0.002	0.0009, 0.0006, 0.0006	[59]
13	DPZ + Empagliflozin + Canagliflozin	Bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage forms (including stress/degradation matrices)	Tablets extracted with suitable solvent, filtered; degradation samples prepared under stress	Acetonitrile : 0.1% Formic Acid Buffer (pH 3.7) = 60:40 (v/v)	Hypersil™ C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	DAD Detection	230, 230, 290	1	0.12, 0.07, 0.29	0.34, 0.25, 1.1	[60]

14	DPZ	API and pharmaceutical dosage form (tablets)	Tablet powder dissolved in solvent, filtered (details not fully specified)	Acetonitrile : Di-potassium hydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 6.5 adjusted with OPA) = 40:60 (v/v)	Agilent C18 (4.6 mm × 150 mm, 5 μm)	PDA Detector	222	1	-	-	[61]
15	DPZ	Bulk drug (API) – DPZgliciflozin with process-related impurities (5-BC, 4-BC)	DPF dissolved in methanol (0.5 mg/mL) - Sonicated for 20 min - Filtered through 0.45 μm membrane filter	Gradient elution: • Phase I – 0.05% aqueous trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) • Phase II – Acetonitrile	Xbridge Phenyl C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	PDA Detector	210	1	5-BC : 0.000165 ppm	5-BC: 0.00054 ppm	[62]
16	DPZ + MET+ Gliclazide+Pioglitazone+Empagliflozin+Saxagliptin+Teneligliptin	Marketed tablet formulations	Stock Solution: 1 mg/mL prepared in Acetonitrile:Water (6:4, v/v) QC Samples: Three levels (LQC, MQC, HQC) prepared by dilution and stored at 4 °C in amber bottles. Assay Preparation: Tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg extracted with 50 mL	Acetonitrile and 0.01% v/v formic acid buffer Optimized Composition: 49.99% acetonitrile, buffer pH 2.5	Type: Waters Reliant™ C18 HPLC column Dimensions: 250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size	Photo-diode array (PDA)	230	1.88	4.44, 4.09, 8.39, 7.348, 8.773, 0.77, 9.53, 5.294, 2.405	13.4650, 2.9816, 22.2691, 26.5849, 23.6222, 16.0431, 8.4648, 12.1348	[63]

			methanol, filtered (Whatman #1 and 0.22 μ m nylon), and diluted to linearity range.								
17	DPZ+ Linagliptin	Bulk drug and tablet dosage form	Tablets containing 5 mg each of DPZgliflozin and Linagliptin were accurately weighed and dissolved in acetonitrile. Further dilutions were made using the mobile phase to achieve a final concentration of 5 μ g/mL each for both drugs.	Acetonitrile: Water (90:10 v/v)	Hypersil C18, 250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m	Photo Diode Array (PDA) Detector	224	1	0.052, 0.094	0.15, 0.28	[64]
18	DPZ	Tablet and Bulk		Methanol:Acetonitrile:Orthophosphoric acid (75:20:5)	C-18	UV detector	246	1	-	-	[65]
19	DPZ	Bulk drug and marketed tablets (Forxiga 10 mg)	Tablet powder (100 mg) dissolved in methanol, sonicated for 8 min, filtered - Diluted appropriately to get 40 μ g/mL test concentration	Methanol: 0.005 M Sodium 1-octanesulphonate buffer (70:30 v/v), pH adjusted to 3.0 with orthophosphoric acid	Phenomenex Gemini-NX C18 (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	UV visible Detector	203	1	0.001	0.009	[66]

20	DPZ + Teneligliptin	Synthetic mixture	40 mg DPZ and 80 mg TENE separately dissolved in diluent (MeOH: Ammonium formate), sonicated - Volume made to 100 mL; further diluted to required concentrations	Methanol : 20 mM Ammonium formate (70:30 v/v), pH not adjusted	Gemini C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	Photodiode Array (PDA) detector	225	1	0.947, 1.355	2.869, 4.107	[67]
21	DPZ	Tablet dosage forms	Tablet powdered, dissolved in methanol or mobile phase, sonicated, filtered (e.g., Whatman No. 41), diluted to required concentration	Phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)	• Waters C18 (25 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	UV or PDA detector	237	1	0.02	0.06	[68]
22	DPZ, SITA	Bulk drug and tablet dosage form	Sitagliptin and DPZgliflozin dissolved in methanol to prepare 1000 μg/ml stock solutions	Phosphate Buffer (pH 5): Acetonitrile: Methanol (40:35:25 v/v/v)	Chemsil C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	UV-VIS	243	1	49.85, 16.45	6.15, 2.03	[69]
23	DPZ	Spiked Human Plasma	Liquid- liquid extraction	Methanol: Double Distilled Water (80:20 % v/v)	Hemsil C18	UV	236	1	-	10 to 50	[70]
24	DPZ, MET	Tablet dosage form Spiked Human Plasma	Tablet: Dissolved in distilled water (DW) Plasma: Solid Phase Extraction (SPE)	2% glacial acetic acid: Acetonitrile (85:15 v/v)	AGILENT C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	UV	230	1	0.18, 0.13, 0.28, 0.74	0.55, 0.39, 0.83, 2.23	[71]

25	DPZ, TNL	Pharmaceutical Formulations	Not Explicitly Detailed	10 mM Ammonium Acetate buffer (in water): Methanol: Acetonitrile (proportions not explicitly stated) (40:50:10 v/v/v)	Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	PDA Detector	224	0.6	-	-	[72]
26	DPZ	Bulk form and marketed formulation	10 mg of Dapagliflozin working standard was dissolved in diluent to 10 ml (1000 ppm). 1 ml was diluted to 10 ml (100 ppm), then 1 ml further diluted to 10 ml (10 ppm). The solution was mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μm filter	Methanol: Phosphate Buffer (0.02 M, pH 3.6) = 45.55% v/v	Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C18 (5 μm, 15 cm × 4.6 mm i.d.)	UV	255	1	5.004	15.164	[73]
27	DPZ, saxagliptin	Human Plasma	Human plasma samples spiked with analytes and internal standard (protein precipitation method, validated)	0.1% ortho phosphoric acid : Acetonitrile (50:50, v/v), pH adjusted to 5.0	Eclipse XDB C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	UV detector	254	1	-	0.05 to 2.00 , 0.01 to 0.50	[74]

28	DPZ, MET	laboratory prepared mixtures as well as a combined pharmaceutical formulation with 1:200 ratio of DPZ: MET.	Stock: 1 mg/mL in methanol, diluted with mobile phase. Tablets: Powdered, dissolved in 30 mL methanol, sonicated 20 min, filtered, diluted; spiking with DPZ (standard addition). Stress: Acidic, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, UV degradation studies.	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.5): Acetonitrile (50:50, v/v)	Symmetry [®] Acclaim [™] RSLC 120 C18 (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 2.2 μm)	UV	225	0.4	1.01, 0.93	3.08, 2.83	[75]
29	DPZ	Tablet Dosage Form	10 mg of DGF was weighed and finely powdered and transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted up to the mark with 7 ml mobile phase, sonicated for 30 minutes and made up the final volume with mobile phase	Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile= 80:20 (v/v)	Develosil ODS HG-5 (C18), 15 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm	UV	292	1	0.09	0.27	[76]
30	DPZ	Pharmaceutical formulations	protein precipitation, liquid-liquid extraction, and solid-phase extraction	Acetonitrile:Phosphate buffer (60:40 v/v, pH 3.5), Methanol:Water (70:30 v/v, 0.1% formic acid), Acetonitrile:Ammonium acetate buffer	C18	UV, RP HPLC, HPTLC	225-285	1	1.2 (UV), 0.15 (HP LC), 125 (H	3.8 (UV), 0.45 (HP LC), 380 (HP TL C)	[77]

				(55:45 v/v, pH 4.5)					PT LC)		
31	DPZ	API under stress degradation conditions	acid degradation sample preparation	0.05% TFA in water (A) and 0.05% TFA in acetonitrile (B)	UHPLC C18 Column	DAD, MS	223-226	0.2-0.4	-	-	[78]
32	DPZ, Sitagliptin	Synthetic Mixture	. 10 mg DPZ + 100 mg SITA in 10 mL methanol .Filtered and diluted further with mobile phase to desired concentrations (10 + 100 µg/mL)	Methyl nitrile (25 parts) : 0.02 M KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (75 parts) with 1 mL triethylamine, pH adjusted to neutral with orthophosphoric acid	Inertsil ODS C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV	210	1	-	-	[79]
33	DPZ, MET	Bulk drug and combined tablet formulation	Individual stock solutions of 1000 µg/mL in water (diluent), sonicated Working solutions diluted to 0.2 µg/mL DAPA & 10 µg/mL MET	Water : Methanol (50:50 v/v)	Phenomenex C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	230	1	345, 263	415, 324	[80]
34	DPZ, Vildagliptin	Pharmaceutical dosage form	.5 mg of each drug dissolved in methanol (stock: 500 µg/mL) .Diluted to working standard: 100 µg/mL	Methanol : 0.01% TFA (pH 2.78) in ratio 95:05 v/v	C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	210	0.8	0.3342, 0.9012	1.0128, 2.7310	[81]

35	DPZ, Vildagliptin	Tablet dosage form	.Tablet powder equivalent to one tablet was sonicated in diluent and filtered .Final dilution: DPZ (5 µg/mL), VIL (50 µg/mL)	KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer : Acetonitrile (70:30 v/v) with 0.1% formic acid, pH adjusted to 5.2	Discovery C18 (4.6 × 150 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	220	1	0.02, 0.07	0.24, 0.72	[82]
36	DPZ, MET	Tablet dosage form	Tablet powder dissolved in methanol with sonication, filtered, then diluted with methanol/diluent	10 mM Ammonium acetate buffer (pH 4) : Methanol : Acetonitrile in 30:65:5 ratio	C8 Thermoquest Hypersil (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	227	0.8	1.121, 6.162	3.396, 18.674	[83]
37	DPZ	Bulk and tablet dosage form	. Tablet powder dissolved in methanol .Ultrasonicate d, filtered, diluted with mobile phase	Phosphate buffer : Acetonitrile : Methanol = 55:40:05 (v/v/v)	ZORBAX C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	225	1	0.0112	0.0339	[84]
38	DPZ, MET	API and Tablet dosage form	.Tablet powder (10 mg DAPA + 500 mg MET) dissolved in methanol . Sonicated and filtered, diluted	Methanol : Water (75:25 v/v) adjusted to pH 3 with 0.05% orthophosphoric acid	C18 Column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	233	1	0.06, 6.09	0.1855, 18.45	[85]
39	DPZ, MET, Saxagliptin	Tablet dosage form	Tablet powder dissolved in diluent, sonicated, filtered, and diluted to: MET (1000 µg/mL), SXG (5 µg/mL), DGF (10 µg/mL)	0.01 N KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (pH 4.8) : Acetonitrile = 65:35 (v/v)	Kromasil C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5.0 µm)	PDA detector	260	1	0.19, 13.85, 0.06	0.57, 41.95, 0.19	[86]

40	DPZ Canagliflozin Empagliflozin	pharmaceutical solid dosage form	Drug substances dissolved in mobile phase, filtered through 0.20 µm membrane, sonicated, and diluted	Gradient of triethanolamine buffer and acetonitrile - 97:3 v/v for 3 min - 85:15 v/v from 3–8 min	Hypersil-T C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detection	280	1.2	0.0067, 0.0075, 0.0073	0.0202, 0.0226, 0.0221	[87]
41	DPZ, MET	Tablet dosage form	Tablet powder (equivalent to 10 mg DAPA and 500 mg MET) was dissolved, sonicated, filtered, and diluted	Acetonitrile : Water (60:40 v/v)	Inertsil ODS C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detection	210	1	0.08, 2.56	0.26, 7.76	[88]
42	DPZ	Drug substance	0.4 mg/mL Dapagliflozin in water:acetonitrile (50:50 v/v), sonicated and filtered	Gradient system: Mobile Phase A: 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid in water Mobile Phase B: Acetonitrile	YMC Pack Pro C18, 250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm	UV detector	225	0.8	0.005	0.016	[89]
43	DPZ, Vildagliptin	Bulk and combined pharmaceutical tablet dosage form (Glyduo, Dapagliflozin:Vildagliptin = 10:100 mg)	.Weigh 10 mg drug, dissolve in water, dilute to 10 ml → 1000 µg/ml. .Further dilute to obtain working standards (100 µg/ml, etc.)	Orthophosphoric acid (OPA) : Acetonitrile in gradient mode, pH adjusted to 5.	Agilent C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	224	0.7	28.7, 0.343	87.04, 1.041	[90]

44	DPZ, Saxagliptin	Combined tablet dosage form (Qtern®: 10 mg DAPA + 5 mg SAXA)	. Weigh 10 mg of each drug, dissolve in 100 mL methanol → 100 µg/mL stock. .Further diluted with mobile phase to get working solutions: . DAPA: 2–12 µg/mL .SAXA: 1–6 µg/mL .Filter through 0.45 µm membrane	80% organic phase (Acetonitrile: Methanol = 40:40) + 20% sodium acetate buffer (pH 4.0)	Hypersil ODS-C18, 250 × 4.6 mm, 2.5 µm	Diode Array Detector	224, 235 Combined detection at 228 nm	1	0.44, 0.26	1.33, 0.78	[91]
45	DPZ, MET	Tablet dosage forms (FARIXIA® and XIGDUO® XR)	Tablets powdered → methanol or methanol/water extraction → filtered → diluted appropriately with methanol or 1:1 methanol/water	0.05 M Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 4.6, adjusted with orthophosphoric acid): Acetonitrile: Methanol (5:4:1 v/v/v)	Hypersil™ ODS C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	236	0.5	0.25, 24.97	0.50, 48.99	[92]
46	DPZ	Tablet dosage form (label claim: 5 mg)	20 tablets weighed, crushed, sonicated in diluent (Water:Methanol 50:50 v/v), filtered through 0.45 µm PVDF filter. - Supernatant diluted as required (final 24 ppm)	Buffer (orthophosphoric acid in water): Acetonitrile: Methanol = 60:37:03 (v/v/v)	Zorbax Eclipse XDB C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	220	1	0.019	0.059	[93]
47	DPZ	Tablet dosage form and	10 mg of Dapagliflozin dissolved in methanol to	Buffer (Tris, pH 7.6) : Methanol = 60:40 (v/v)	Zorbax Eclipse Plus C8 (150 × 4.6	UV detector	224	1	0.207	0.693	[94]

		Bulk drug	prepare stock solution (1000 µg/mL) - Working standard prepared by diluting with methanol to 100 µg/mL - Sample: Aliquots (0.1–3.2 mL) diluted in 10 mL methanol		mm, 5 µm)						
48	DPZ, Linagliptin	Tablet dosage form and Bulk drug	Tablet powder equivalent to 50 mg DAPA + 25 mg LINA extracted in methanol, sonicated, filtered, diluted	Chloroform : Methanol : Ethyl acetate : Formic acid (3:4:3:0.5, v/v)	Silica gel 60 F254 (10 × 10 cm) plates, 100 µm	UV detector	224	-	21 5.3 8, 22 6.1 6	652. 69, 685. 36	[95]
49	DPZ, MET, Saxagliptin	Pharmaceutical tablets (Qtern met XR)	Tablet powder (avg wt. 1285.6 mg) sonicated in diluent, filtered, and diluted	Acetonitrile : 0.01N KH ₂ PO ₄ (70:30, v/v); pH adjusted to 3.5 with OPA	Agilent C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV detector	238	1.2	0.0 4, 0.5 4, 0.0 2	0.12 , 1.62 , 0.05	[96]
50	LGZsulafate MET hydrochloride	pharmaceutical formulations	-	ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (pH 3.0) and a premix of methanol and acetonitrile (80:20)	Phenomenex Strong Cation Exchange (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 10 µm) column	PDA detector	251	1	-	-	[97]
51	LGZ	Rat plasma forms	Fast flow protein precipitation	Acetonitrile-water-formic acid(60:40:0.25, v/v/v)	Zorbax C18, 2.1×100mm, 3.5 µm	LC-MS/MS, MRM mode, ESI positive ion	290	0.2	-	50n g/ml	[98]

52	LGZ	Bulk drug and tablet formulation	50 mg tablet powder dissolved in diluent, sonicated, filtered, and diluted to 50 µg/mL.	Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and Acetonitrile in a 70:30 v/v with a pH of 4.0, adjusted using orthophosphoric acid	Phenomenex Luna Column with dimension of 250 cm × 4.6 mm × 5 µm	UV	250	1	0.8	2.5	[99]
53	LGZ, Glimepride	Tablet dosage form (marketed product LOBG-G1).	weigh 25 mg each of GPR and LGL into separate 25 mL flasks, add ~15 mL ACN, sonicate 18 min, make to volume with ACN; prepare working solutions (GPR 100 µg/mL, LGL 50 µg/mL) by serial dilution with mobile phase; filter 0.45 µm nylon.	Acetonitrile : 10 mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3.5) = 65:35 (v/v).	Enable C18 G, 250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm; column oven at 40 °C.	PDA/UV	235	1	1.66, 1.77	5.05, 5.39	[100]
54	LGZ	tablet formulation	25 mg LOB dissolved in 50 ml diluent (500 µg/ml, Stock I). From Stock I, diluted to prepare Stock II (20 µg/ml). Working standard: 2 ml of Stock II diluted to 10 ml with mobile phase (4 µg/ml). Tablet sample:	Acetonitrile :Methanol:water in 0.1% Triethylamine (70:30:10, v/v/v)	Phenomenex Luna C18, 250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm.	UV	248	1	0.342	1.037	[101]

			Powder equivalent to 0.5 mg LOB dissolved in 25 ml flask with diluent, sonicated 10 min, filtered, further diluted to 4 µg/ml								
55	LGZ sulfate	Tablet dosage form	20 tablets was determined. Sample stock solution was prepared by dissolving tablet powder equivalent to 0.5 mg of LOB and was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask. Then 15 ml diluent was added and sonicated for 10 mins to ensure complete solubilization of drug. After sonication, volume was made up to the mark with diluent. Filter the sample stock solution with Whatman filter paper and 2ml of the solution was further diluted to 10 ml to get final concentration	Acetonitrile : 1% glacial acetic acid (70:30 v/v)	Kromasil C18 G, 250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm; ambient temperature; injection volume 20 µL	SPD 20A UV detector	254	1	0.04	0.12	[102]

56	LGZ, Glimepride	Bulk drug & Tablet dosage form	Twenty tablets were weighed, powdered... equivalent to average weight (0.267 mg) taken in 100 mL volumetric flask → dissolved in methanol → sonicated 30 min → filtered (0.45 µm membrane filter) → diluted with mobile phase to 100 µg/mL	Acetonitrile : Phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) = 60:40 v/v (isocratic), Methanol as diluent	Shim-pack C18, 250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm	PDA	254	1	6.348, 11.923	9.821, 20.012	[103]
57	LGZ, Glimepride	Pharmaceutical dosage form	Simple extraction using methanol (tablet powder dissolved, sonicated, filtered)	Acetonitrile : Water (65:35 v/v, pH 3 adjusted with 1% OPA)	Shim-pack solar C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV	224	1	0.2765, 0.1938	0.08381, 0.5874	[104]
58	LGZSulphate, Sitagliptin	Synthetic Mixture	Dissolved in methanol (diluent). Serial dilutions prepared	Water (pH 3.0, adjusted with orthophosphoric acid): Methanol (35:65 % v/v)	Agilent C18 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV	265	1	0.007, 0.224	0.0053, 0.68	[105]
59	LGZ, MET	Tablet dosage form	Tablet powder equivalent to 0.5 mg LGZ & 500 mg MET dissolved in methanol, sonicated 20 min, filtered, diluted with diluent	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate buffer (pH 2.5, adjusted with OPA) (70:5:25 v/v/v)	Cosmosphere C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	UV VIS	250, 234	0.8	0.001, 0.3019	0.0031, 0.9151	[106]

60	LGZ	Pharmaceutical formulation & human plasma	Protein precipitation (for plasma)	15 mM KH ₂ PO ₄ -Acetonitrile; 10:80 v/v	Zodiac-100 C8 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm ID)	SPD 10AVP	230	1	2.05	6.85	[107]
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3.3 HPTLC

HPTLC is a more advanced form of thin-layer chromatography (TLC) that allows for precise, accurate, and reproducible drug separation and quantification. Dapagliflozin (DPZ) and its combinations were successfully estimated using HPTLC under a variety of chromatographic conditions. The maximum detection wavelength for DPZ analysis was reported to be 252 nm^[113] and the maximum saturation time observed was 40 minutes^[109]. Almost all methods used aluminium plates precoated with silica gel 60 F254 (Merck) as the stationary phase, highlighting their reliability and reproducibility^[108-120]. In terms of mobile phase composition, several solvent systems were used depending on the drug combinations; however, the

most commonly used mobile phase was a mixture of acetonitrile, benzene, glacial acetic acid^[118].

High-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC) is widely used in analytical research to assess Lobeglitazone, especially in combination formulations. With a similar saturation time of 20 ± 5 minutes, the highest detection wavelength recorded in the methods under consideration is 238 nm. While acetonitrile with ammonium acetate in methanol and mixes like ethyl acetate, benzene, hexane were often used mobile phases, the majority of research used silica gel 60 F254 precoated aluminium plates as the stationary phase^[122]. For analytes such as Lobeglitazone and its combinations with glimepiride or metformin, these combinations were often chosen because they were effective in producing crisp, well-resolved spots^[121-122].

Table 3: Representative HPTLC methods for the analysis of Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone

Sr No.	Drugs	Stationary phase	Mobile phase	RF value	Detection wavelength	Saturation time	Linearity range (ng/band)	LOD (ng/band)	LOQ (ng/band)	Ref.
1	DPZ	Merck TLC plates silica gel 60 F254 (10 × 10 cm, 75–125 μm layer thickness)	Chloroform: Methanol (9:1 v/v)	0.21 ± 0.004	223 nm	30min	400 – 1200	1.2083	3.6616	[108]

2	DPZ Linagliptin	Pre-coated silica gel 60 F254 aluminium plates (10 × 10 cm, 0.2 mm thickness, E. Merck, Germany)	Toluene:Chloroform:Methanol:Triethylamine (7:2:1:0.2, v/v/v/v)	DPZ: 0.23 Lina: 0.40	224 nm	40min	200 – 1200 (for both drugs)	25.80, 13.09	72.22, 42.14	[109]
3	DPZ Propanediol Monohydrate (DPM) Metformin HCL (MFH) Vildagliptin (VGP)	Silica Gel 60 F254 precoated aluminium plate	Ethyl acetate: 3% w/v ammonium acetate in ethanol: Triethylamine (7.0: 3.0: 0.3, v/v)	0.40 0.19 0.60	220nm	15min	300 - 900 15,000 - 45,000 3000 - 9000	100 50 100	300 150 300	[110]
4	DPZ Metoprolol Succinate (MET)	Pre-coated silica gel 60 F254 aluminium sheets (0.2 mm thickness, 10 × 10 cm)	n-Butanol: Ethyl acetate: Triethylamine (6:4:0.1, v/v/v)	DPZ: 0.67 MET: 0.35	223 nm	30 ± 5 min	200–1200, 1000–6000	21.97, 223.58	66.60, 677.53	[111]
5	DPZ Metformin (MET) Saxagliptin (SAXA)	Pre-coated silica gel 60 F254 HPTLC aluminium plates	Methanol: 0.5% aqueous ammonium sulphate (8:2, v/v), pH 5.5	DPZ: 0.88 MET: 0.21 SAXA: 0.46	222nm	20min	250–750, 50,000–150,000, 250–750	17.90, 2962.2, 11.08	54.29, 8976.4, 33.59	[112]

6	Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate (DPZ) Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate (SITA) Metformin Hydrochloride (MET)	Precoated silica gel aluminium HPTLC Plate 60 F254 (10×10 cm, 100 µm dimensions)	Ethyl acetate: Methanol: Ammonia: Glacial acetic acid (6.8: 2.7: 0.4: 0.1, V/V/V/V)	DPZ: 0.771 SITA: 0.597 MET: 0.257	252 nm	20min	300–800, 3000– 8000, 30000– 80000	413, 1507.8, 25605. 8	1252.7, 4569.2, 77593. 5	[113]
7	DPZ, Linagliptin (LINA)	Precoated silica gel aluminium plate 60 F254, (10 × 10 cm), 100 µm thickness	Chloroform: Methanol: Ethyl acetate: 1% Formic acid (3:4:3:0.5, v/v)	DPZ: 0.66 LINA: 0.20	224nm	20 min	3000– 9000, 1500–4500	215.38, 226.16	652.69, 685.36	[114]
8	Dapagliflozin Monohydrate (DPZ) Telmisartan (TEL)	Aluminium plates precoated with silica gel 60 F254	Ethyl acetate: Toluene (8:2, v/v)	DPZ:0.19 TEL: 0.41	236nm	25min	200–500, 800–2000	16.49, 70.08	49.97, 212.34	[115]
9	DPZ, Vildagliptin (VILG)	Silica gel 60 F254 aluminium plates (10 × 10 cm)	Toluene: Ethyl Acetate: Methanol: Ammonia (6.0: 2.0: 2.0: 0.1, v/v/v/v)	DPZ = 0.54 VILG = 0.28	217nm	15min	200 – 1400, 2000 – 14000	2.34, 5.82	7.10, 17.63	[116]
10	DPZ	Aluminium HPTLC plates precoated with silica gel 60 F254 (Merck, 10 ×	Methanol: Toluene: Ammonium acetate	0.29 ± 0.05	250 nm	15 min	100–1000	16.7	50.5	[117]

		10 cm, layer thickness 150–200 µm)	(6.9: 3: 0.1, v/v/v)							
11	DPZ, Vildagliptin	Pre-coated silica gel 60 F254 aluminium plates	Acetonitrile: Benzene: Glacial Acetic Acid (9:1:2 v/v/v)	-	210 nm	-	-	-	-	[118]
12	DPZ, Metformin (MET), Saxagliptin (SAX)	Merck HPTLC silica gel plates	Chloroform: Methanol: Water: Acetic Acid (7.4:2.6:0.5:0.01 v/v)	-	224 nm	-	-	-	-	[118]
13	DPZ, Metoprolol (METO)	Aluminium TLC plates pre-coated with silica gel 60-F254 (10 cm × 10 cm)	Toluene: Chloroform: Methanol: Glacial acetic acid (4.5: 2: 3: 0.5, v/v/v/v)	DPZ: 0.26 ± 0.02 METO: 0.74 ± 0.02	235nm	15min	400–1200, 1000–6000	26.58, 51.81	80.57, 157.00	[119]
14	DPZ, Saxagliptin (SAX)	Silica gel 60 F254 aluminium plates (20 × 10 cm, 250 µm thickness)	Hexane: Methanol: Ethyl acetate (4: 2: 4, v/v/v)	DPZ: 0.60 SAX: 0.18	DGF: 225 nm SAX: 210 nm	20 min	50–550 ng/spot for both	DPZ: 12 ng/spot SAX: 15 ng/spot	DPZ: 36 ng/spot SAX: 45 ng/spot	[120]
15	LBZ, Metformin Hydrochloride	Silica gel 60 F254 precoated aluminium plates	Acetonitrile: 1 M Ammonium Acetate in Methanol: Toluene: Triethylamine (1.5: 2.5: 4: 0.2 v/v/v/v)	Lobeglitazone: ~0.36 Metformin: ~0.61	237 nm	15 min	100–1500, 1000–15,000	8.17, 271.34	24.75, 822.24	[121]

16	LBZ, Glimepiride (GLM)	Aluminium plates layered with silica gel 60 F ₍₂₅₄₎	Ethyl acetate: Benzene: Hexane (4: 3: 1, v/v/v)	LBZ: 0.68 ± 0.001 GLM: 0.48 ± 0.002	238nm	20 ± 5 minutes	100–2000, 200–4000	23.86, 58.26	72.32, 176.55	[122]
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3.4 LC-MS

The LC–MS/MS has been widely applied for quantification of Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone in bulk, plasma, and formulations [140]. For both drug, among the various chromatographic system, C18 columns were the most commonly used stationary phase due to their reproducibility and efficiency [123–149]. The mobile phase typically consisted of acetonitrile with formic acid or ammonium buffers, with acetonitrile – formic acid mixtures being most preferred for enhanced sensitivity and resolution [123–149]. Flow rates for Dapagliflozin varied from

0.2 mL/min to 1.2 mL/min, with 0.2 mL/min [126,130] most frequently applied for optimal sensitivity and resolution, while 1.2 mL/min [128] was the highest reported. For Lobeglitazone, flow rates ranged from 0.2 mL/min to 0.25 mL/min [144,146,148,149]. Injection volumes generally ranged from 2 to 20 µL [126,135,137] for Dapagliflozin and 5 to 10 µL for Lobeglitazone. Detection for both drugs was performed on triple quadrupole mass spectrometers using electro spray ionization (ESI) in positive MRM mode, which ensured superior selectivity, sensitivity, and robustness in quantification [123–149]. Analytical methods using LC-MS [123–149] are shown in table 4.

Table 4: Representative LC-MS methods for the analysis of Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone.

Sr No.	Drug	Stationary phase	Mobile phase	Flow rate (ml/min)	Column temp	Injection volume	MS detection	Linearity range (ng/ml)	LOD (ng/ml)	LOQ (ng/ml)	Ref.
1	DPZ Propionidol Monohydrate (DPG)	BDS Hypersil C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 µm particle size)	Gradient elution: Water (A) and Acetonitrile (B)	1	35 °C	20 µL	ESI positive mode (ESI+); m/z scan range 50–1000; source voltage 3.5 kV; source temperature 350 °C; N ₂ curtain gas 10 L/min	2.0–200 ppm	8.59	28.34	[123]
2	DPZ SAXA (SG)	Hypersil Gold C18 column (50 mm × 3.0 mm, 5 µm)	10 mM Ammonium acetate: Methanol (20:80, v/v)	0.5	30 °C	20 µL	ESI positive ionization, MRM transitions: DG (m/z 410.2 → 250.6), SG	50.0 – 10,000.0 pg/mL	-	50 pg/mL	[124]

							(316.1 → 272.4)				
3	DPZ	Hypersil Gold C18 column (50 × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm)	Water: Acetonitrile (MeCN)	0.3	40 °C	5 μL	MRM, ESI negative mode, (m/z) 407.27 → 329.19 for DPZ, 449.29 → 371.18 for IS	2.50 - 250.0	-	2.5	[125]
4	DPZ Metformin	Agilent Infinity Lab Poroshell 120 EC-C18 (2.1 × 100 mm, 2.7 μm)	5 mM ammonium acetate: acetonitrile (20:80, v/v), isocratic	0.2	35 °C	10 μL	ESI-positive mode, MRM transitions: DPZ: m/z 426.20 → 107.20 Metformin: m/z 130.10 → 60.10	25–500, 100–2000	6.83, 29.45	20.70, 89.24	[126]
5	DPZ Sorafenib (SOR)	XSelect HSS T3 column (2.1 mm × 100 mm, 2.5 μm)	0.1% formic acid in water: 5mM ammonium acetate (phase A): acetonitrile (phase B)	1	40 °C	5 μL	MRM, SOR: m/z 465.3 → 270.1 DPZ: 426.1 → 167.2	5-2000, 5-5000	-	-	[127]
6	DPZ	Infinity Lab Poroshell 120 column (50 × 3.5 mm, 5 μm)	Acetonitrile: 25 mM ammonium acetate (pH 4.1) (65:35 v/v)	1.2	40 °C	5 μL	Triple quadrupole MS (Bruker EVOC LC-TQ), Turbo ion spray source, polarity switching (positive & negative mode), MRM transitions: m/z 467.1 → 329.1 for DPZ	0.05 – 150	0.07	0.35	[128]

7	DPZ SAX A	Ace Phenyl column (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	Acetonitrile: 5 mM ammonium acetate buffer (70:30, v/v, isocratic)	0.8	40 °C	2 L	Positive ion mode, ESI; MRM transition m/z 409.14 → 135	0.502 - 227, 0.103 - 76.402	-	0.10, 0.50	[129]
8	DPZ	Waters ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 (100 × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm, 130 Å)	(Positive mode) A: 0.1% formic acid in deionized water; B: 0.1% formic acid in methanol - (Negative mode)A: 0.02% acetic acid in deionized water; B: 0.02% acetic acid in acetonitrile	0.2	50 °C	2 μL	Bruker Compact™ QTOF with ESI source; scan range 50–1000 m/z; capillary voltage ±4500 V	-	-	-	[130]
9	DPZ (DP G) SAX A (SX G)	Hypersil C18 (50 mm × 4 mm, 5 μm)	0.1% formic acid: acetonitrile (25:75 v/v)	0.7	45 °C	-	(MRM transition) DPZ: m/z 409.14 →135.0 SXG: m/z 316.2→180.13	0.5 - 1500, 2.00 - 2000.0	-	1, 4	[131]
10	DPZ	ACE 5CN (150×4.6 mm, 5 μm)	Water: Acetonitrile	-	-	-	Negative ion electrospray ionization mode	5 - 40 μg/mL	-	-	[132]

11	DPZ Prop anedi ol Mon ohyd rate (DPZ) Vilda glipti n (VIL D)	Zorbax C18 column (5 µm, 150 × 4.6 mm)	Acetonitr ile: 10 mM ammoniu m acetate buffer (pH 5, adjusted with formic acid) = 30:70 (v/v)	1	35 °C	-	.LC-ESI- MS/MS (API- 2000) .Electrospray Ionization (ESI), Positive ion mode .Quadrupole analyzer .Detection by MRM (Multiple Reaction Monitoring) scan	0.5 – 1.5 µg/ml 5 – 15 µg/ml	0.1 10 µg/ ml 0.7 09 µg/ ml	0.333 µg/m l, 2.147 µg/m l	[133]
12	DPZ Metf ormi n	ACN 5CN (150 × 4.6 mm, 5µm)	Acetonitr ile: 15mM ammoniu m acetate, pH 4.5 (70:30, v/v)	-	-	-	Ion transition using MRM, both positive and negative mode DPZ: m/z 467.1→329.1 MET: m/z 130.1→60.1	0.10 - 200, 1.00 - 2000	0.0 3, 0.3 9	0.1, 1.0	[134]
13	DPZ	Core-shell Ascentis® Express C- 18 column (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm; Supelco)	0.1% formic acid in water: acetonitr ile (65:35, v/v) (isocratic elution)	0.5	30 °C	10 µL	3200 QTRAP (Applied Biosystems, MDS Sciex) Mode: Negative ionization (ESI-)	50–150 µg/mL	0.2 8 µg/ mL	0.86 µg/m L	[135]
14	DPZ, SAX A	Agilent Eclipse Plus C18 column (150 mm×4.6 mm,3.6 µm)	Solvent A: 0.01% ammonia solution Solvent B: Acetonitr ile Gradient: 0.0–3.2 min: 35% B 3.2–5.0 min: 55% B 5.0–5.5	1	-	5 µL	API-4000 triple quadrupole with ESI source. Polarity: Switching mode (positive for SAX, negative for DPZ).	5 – 2000, 0.2 – 80	-	5, 0.2	[136]

			min: 35% B								
15	DPZ	SunFire™ C18, 50 × 2.1 mm, 5 µm	Isocratic: Water/Ac etonitrile (60:40, v/v) Gradient: 20% to 80% acetonitri le in 2.5 min, hold at 80% for 2.5 min	0.3	30 °C	10 µl	TSQ Quantum Ultra (Thermo Fisher) Ionization: Heated electrospray ionization, negative mode	5 – 2000	-	5	[137]
16	DPZ and D3O G	Waters XSELECT HSS T3 (2.1 × 100 mm, 3.5 µm)	-	0.3	-	-	LC-MS/MS (ESI)	5-50, 50-500	-	5, 50	[138]
17	DPZ and D3O G	Poroshell 120 EC- C18	Gradient of 10 mM ammoniu m formate / MeOH	-	-	-	Negative ESI, MRM	2–800 µg/L,	-	-	[139]
18	DPZ, Lina glipti n (LN G)	Eclipse Plus C18 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm,5 µm)	Gradient elution of 0.1% v/v formic acid and acetonitri le	0.7	-	-	UHPLC/ESI- MS/MS	50–150 µg/mL 25–75 µg/mL	DP Z: 5 µg/ mL LN G: 4 µg/ mL	DPZ: 15 µg/m L LNG : 12 µg/m L	[140]
19	DPZ, Emp aglifi ozin, Metf ormi n Lina glipti n	Zorbax SB C18 (octadecyl silica) column, 50 mm × 3.6 mm i.d.,5 µm	10 mm Ammoni um Acetate buffer (pH 5): Acetonitr ile (20:80 v/v)	0.5	-	-	Triple quadrupole, ESI (+/- mode) ,photomultipli er tube detector	15.8 – 316, 7.5 – 150, 6 – 120	5.2 00, 2.4 50, 1.9 50	1.50, 7.5, 6.0	[141]

20	DPZ, Empagliflozin, Canagliflozin	-	gradient of water with formic acid + acetonitrile	-	-	-	tandem mass spectrometry	10 – 10,000 pg/mg	5 pg/mg	10 pg/mg	[142]
21	DPZ, Bisoprolol fumarate	Inertsil ODS-3V (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	Gradient: KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (pH 4.2) & acetonitrile (two compositions: 90:10 & 25:75)	1	-	-	-	2–24 μg/mL, 1–12 μg/mL	-	-	[143]
22	Lobeglitazone (CKD-501)	Luna C18 column (50 × 2.0 mm, 3 μm; Phenomenex, USA)	A: 0.1% formic acid in water B: 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile	Sample loading: 4 mL/min (aqueous A, 40 s) Analytical run: 0.25 mL/min	-	10 μL	API 3000 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer Ionization: ESI, positive ion mode	0.5 – 1000, 0.2 – 250	-	0.5, 0.2	[144]
23	Lobeglitazone (CKD-501)	Zorbax C18 column (2.1 mm × 100 mm, 3.5 μm)	Acetonitrile: Water: Formic acid (60:40:0.25, v/v/v)	0.2	30 °C	5 μL	LC-MS/MS using MRM: m/z 482.0 → 258.0 (analyte); 358.0 → 135.0 (IS)	50–10,000 ng/mL (R > 0.999)	-	50	[145]
24	Lobeglitazone (LBZ) and its major	Metabolite identification: Waters Atlantis dC18 column, 2.1 × 100	Metabolite identification: Methanol (0.1% formic acid)	0.25	25 °C	10 μL (metabolite identification)	LC-MS/MS with electrospray ionization (ESI) in positive mode ion	LBZ: 1–500, M1: 1–1000	-	1 (for both LBZ & M1)	[146]

	r meta bolite M1	mm, 3 µm Quantificat ion in plasma: Phenyl-3 analytical column, 50 × 2.0 mm, 4 µm	Deionize d water (0.1% formic acid)80:2 0 (v/v) Quantific ation in plasma: 0.1% formic acid in methanol – 10 mM ammoniu m formate (80:20, v/v)			ion) 5 µL (plas ma quan tifica tion)					
25	Lobe glitaz one Sitag liptin	Waters ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 2.1 mm × 50 mm, 1.7 µm)	Lobeglita zone: A: 0.1% formic acid in distilled water B: 0.1% formic acid in acetonitri le Sitaglipti n: A: 0.5% formic acid in distilled water B: Acetonitr ile	0.4	not repor ted	Lobe glita zone : 10 µL Sitag liptin : 2 µL	LC–MS/MS with electrospray ionization (ESI) in positive ion mode Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM)	1 – 250, 1 – 1000	-	-	[147]
26	Lobe glitaz one (CK D- 501)	Luna C18, 3.0 µm, 50 × 2.0 mm (Phenomen ex, Torrance, CA)	Acetonitr ile–water mixture containin g 0.1% formic acid	0.25	-	Plas ma 10 µL Urin e 50 µL	API 3000 triple quadrupole, positive ionization, MRMmode	Plasma: 0.5 – 1000 Urine: 0.2 – 250	-	0.5(p lasm a) 0.2(u rine)	[148]

27	Lobeglitazone, Metformin	Atlantis HILIC silica column (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 2.0 μm)	5 mM ammonium formate (pH 3.0) in acetonitrile-water mixture (70:30, v/v)	0.25	-	5 μL	LC-MS/MS, MRM mode	0.5 – 100, 20 – 3000	-	0.5, 20	[149]
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3.5 GC

Cholleti Vijay Kumar et al. developed and validated a novel static headspace gas chromatography (HSGC) method with flame ionization detection (FID) for the analysis of residual solvents in Dapagliflozin amorphous.

In their study, the authors measured 12 residual solvents. They are methanol, ethanol, diethyl ether, methyl acetate, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, cyclohexane, isopropyl acetate, methyl isobutyl ketone, toluene, and chlorobenzene by using a DB-624 column (60 m × 0.53 mm I.D., 3.0 μm) with nitrogen as the carrier gas and N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone as the diluent. The method exhibited exceptional resolution, linearity (correlation coefficients >0.9936), accuracy (recoveries 97.1–103.0%), and robustness, with LOD well below ICH-recommended thresholds. Nitrogen was used as the carrier gas under a constant pressure of 7.0 psi, and the injection was performed in split mode (1:5) with an injection volume of 1 μL. The inlet and detector (FID) temperatures were maintained at 140 °C and 250 °C, respectively, with hydrogen, air, and makeup gas flows of 40, 400, and 25 mL/min. The oven temperature program began at 40 °C (hold 10 min), ramped at 8 °C/min to 190 °C (hold 10 min), and finally increased to 240 °C at 50 °C/min (hold 5 min), providing a total run time of 45 minutes. For headspace sampling, vial equilibration at 90 °C for 10 min with high shaking, a loop temperature of 95 °C, and a transfer line temperature of 100 °C were found optimal. These conditions facilitated robust separation and detection of 12 residual solvents in Dapagliflozin, with satisfactory resolution, precision,

and recovery, thus complying with ICH Q2 (R1) validation guidelines [\[150\]](#). This work highlights both the therapeutic significance of Dapagliflozin and the analytical importance of developing validated GC methods for ensuring pharmaceutical quality and regulatory compliance.

4. CHALLENGES

Although researchers have worked a lot on finding good analytical methods for Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone, some problems are still there. One big issue is that both drugs are found in plasma in very small amounts, so highly sensitive methods like LC-MS/MS are needed to measure them. At the same time, detection is not always simple because natural biomolecules in the sample can interfere, which often means extra preparation steps. Another difficulty is that these two drugs do not share the same chemical behaviour, so each method has to be adjusted differently — for example, the choice of mobile phase, column, or detection wavelength. Stability also becomes a hurdle, especially when the drugs face stress or start degrading, making the validation process harder. On top of this, there are not many studies that focus on stability-indicating or bioanalytical methods especially for Lobeglitazone and no method has been published for the combination of Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Dapagliflozin and Lobeglitazone stand out as valuable oral agents for type 2 diabetes mellitus, each working through different mechanisms to deliver therapeutic benefits. Researchers have explored several methods for their analysis separately

in both biological samples and pharmaceutical products but there has been no method published for combination of the both drugs. No approaches such as UV spectrophotometry, HPLC, HPTLC and LC-MS are applied for this combination and its own strengths in terms of sensitivity, accuracy. These techniques not only support everyday quality checks and pharmacokinetic evaluations but also ensure that regulatory standards are met while opening doors for future studies.

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REFERENCES

1. Kasichayanula S, Liu X, LaCreta F, Griffen SC, Boulton DW. Clinical pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of dapagliflozin, a selective inhibitor of sodium-glucose co-transporter type 2. *Clinical pharmacokinetics*. 2014 Jan;53(1):17-27.
2. Anderson SL. Dapagliflozin efficacy and safety: a perspective review. *Therapeutic advances in drug safety*. 2014 Dec;5(6):242-54.
3. Seo DH, Suh YJ, Cho Y, Ahn SH, Seo S, Hong S, Lee YH, Choi YJ, Lee E, Kim SH. Effect of Dapagliflozin in Combination with Lobeglitazone and Metformin in Korean patients with type 2 diabetes in real-world clinical practice. *Yonsei medical journal*. 2022 Aug 18;63(9):825.
4. European Medicines Agency (EMA). Forxiga: EPAR – Public assessment report. London: EMA; 2012.
5. Bae J, Park T, Kim H, Lee M, Cha BS. Lobeglitazone: a novel thiazolidinedione for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes & metabolism journal*. 2021 Apr 19;45(3):326-36.
6. Balamurugan Jr M, Sarumathy Sr S, Robinson Jr R. Lobeglitazone and Its Therapeutic Benefits: A Review.
7. Maciel AB, de Meira RZ, Murakami FS, de Oliveira PR, Bernardi LS. In vitro dissolution profile of dapagliflozin: Development, method validation, and analysis of commercial tablets. *International journal of analytical chemistry*. 2017;2017(1):2951529.
8. Joshi S, Tandon M, Kodgule R, Wu W, Jadhao V, Suryawanshi S, Barkate H. Randomized, Double-blind, Phase III Trial of Lobeglitazone Add-on to Metformin in Type 2 Diabetes (SENSITIZE INDIA). *The Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*. 2024 Jan 1;72(1):32-42.
9. Marina Juliet A, Thanikachalam PV. Development and Validation of QBD-Assisted Using Central Composite Design RP-HPLC Method for Lobeglitazone Sulfate and Glimipiride in Bulk and Its Combined Dosage Form. *Chromatographia*. 2025 May;88(5):381-93.
10. Gulhane PD, Jawarkar SG. Bioanalytical method development and validation for Determination of lobeglitazone in human plasma. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*. 2023;5(05):8103-16.
11. Sen DB, Jatu S, Maheshwari RA, Zanwar AS, Velmurugan R, Sen AK. New eco-friendly UV-spectroscopic methods for simultaneous assessment of dapagliflozin, saxagliptin and Metformin in ternary mixture. *Indian J Pharm Edu Res*. 2023 Apr 1;57(2):559-69.
12. Kavana DC, GS NK. Recent Progress in Analytical Method Development and Validation of Dapagliflozin. *Journal of Pharma Insights and Research*. 2025 Apr 5;3(2):090-7.
13. Raveendra BG, Kumar RA, Shaheen SD, Greeshma A, Satyanarayana M, Manikanta RS, Syam CP. A novel stability-indicating method for the simultaneous estimation of saxagliptin and dapagliflozin in rat serum by using UV spectroscopy. *Pharm Anal Acta*. 2018;9(3):1-5.
14. Chaudhari SS. Quantitative Estimation of Dapagliflozin in Blood Plasma by Using UV Spectroscopy. *J Develop Drugs*. 2019;10(2):608.
15. Jadhav SA, Bhilare NA, Chandanshive B, Dyade GK, Lunkad AS. Sustainable Green Analytical Chemistry: Spectrophotometric Method

- Development of Dapagliflozin and Omeprazole by Using Eco-friendly Solvent. *Current Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2023:179-87.
16. Pathak S, Mishra P. A review on analytical methods of dapagliflozin: An updat. *Int J Pharm Qual Assur*. 2020;11(3):355-60.
 17. Patel A, Jadeja P, Mashru R. Analytical method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin and Tenueligliptin hydrobromide hydrate from synthetic mixture by three different UV spectrophotometric methods. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2022 Apr 14;11(7):770-83.
 18. Sauer AJ, Chang J, Fu Z, Valenzuela Ripoll C, Cho Y, Guo Z, Jones P, Selvaraj S, Windsor SL, Husain M, Inzucchi SE. Dapagliflozin's Association With Cardiorenal Outcomes and Apolipoprotein M Levels in HFREF Patients: Insights From DEFINE-HF. *JACC: Advances*. 2025 Jun 1;4(6_Part_2):101800.
 19. Karuna PC, China E, Rao MB. Unique UV spectrophotometric method for reckoning of Dapagliflozin in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. *J Chem Pharm Res*. 2015;7(9):45-9.
 20. Patel AB, Patel PH. Development and validation of HPTLC method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate, sitagliptin phosphate monohydrate and metformin hydrochloride using doe approach. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*. 2025 Jan 1;18(1):309-17.
 21. Jani BR, Shah KV, Kapupara PP. Development and validation of UV spectroscopic first derivative method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and metformin hydrochloride in synthetic mixture. *J Bioequiv*. 2015;1(1):102.
 22. Bhavya S, Nandhini M. Simultaneous method development and validation of combined dosage form dapagliflozin and vildagliptin in bulk and combined tablet dosage form by UV spectrophotometer. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*. 2024;17(4):53-9.
 23. Sen AK, Khatariya SB, Sen DB, Maheshwari RA, Zanwar AS, Velmurugan R. Various innovative UV spectroscopic methodologies for concurrent estimation of dapagliflozin and vildagliptin in combined tablet. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*. 2023 Sep 4;13(9):213-23.
 24. Vadla S, Putta V, Nadipudi S, Bilakanti S, Kudumula N. Estimation Method for Dapagliflozin in Bulk and Marketed Dosage Form: Development and Validation by UV-Spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Phytopharmacological Research (eIJPPR)*. 2023 Aug;13(4):1-6.
 25. Shah KV, Kapupara PP, Jani BR. Development, and validation of UV spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and metformin hydrochloride in synthetic mixture. *International Journal of Research and Development in Pharmacy & Life Sciences*. 2015 May 15;4(3):1569-76.
 26. Mante GV, Gupta KR, Hemke AT. Estimation of dapagliflozin from its tablet formulation by UV-spectrophotometry. *Pharm Methods*. 2017 Jul 1;8(2):102-7.
 27. Bhadauria RS, Agarwal V. Development and validation of UV spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and saxagliptin in marketed formulation. *J Drug Deliv Ther*. 2019; 9:1160-4.
 28. Bhavyasri K, Surekha T, Sumakanth M. A Novel Method Development and Validation of Dapagliflozin and Metormin Hydrochloride using Simultaneous Equation Method by UV-Visible Spectroscopy in Bulk and Combined Pharmaceutical Formulation including Forced Degradation Studies. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2020 Aug 1;12(8):1100-5.
 29. Pandya S, Patil P, Kalsara K, Upadhyay U. A review article on UV and HPLC method for dapagliflozin and linagliptin in synthetic mixture. *Int J Pharm Res Appl*. 2023;8(3):983-990.
 30. Meira de RZ, Maciel AB, Murakami FS, de Oliveira PR, Bernardi LS. In vitro dissolution profile of dapagliflozin: Development, method validation, and analysis of commercial tablets. *International journal of analytical chemistry*. 2017;2017(1):2951529.
 31. Patel M, Vyas N, Shah H, Shah U, Patel A, Chokshi A. Analytical Methods for Simultaneous Estimation of SGLT2 Inhibitor And DPP-4 Inhibitor in Their Combination for Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Lett Appl Nano bioscience*. 2020; 10:1799-815.

32. Hiral S. Popaniya, Dinesh K. Dangar, Chintankumar J. Tank. A Concise Review Based On Analytical Methods For Estimation Of Dapagliflozin And Linagliptin In Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *Asian Journal Of Pharmaceutical Analysis*. 2024; 14(4):275-2
33. Surekha T, Bhavyasri K, Sumakanth M. A Novel Method Development And Validation Of Dapagliflozin And Metformin Hydrochloride Using Simultaneous Equation Method By UV-Visible Spectroscopy In Bulk And Combined Pharmaceutical Formulation Including Forced Degradation Studies. *Journal Of Pharmaceutical Sciences And Research*. 2020 Aug 1;12(8):1100-5.
34. Tiwari G, Maheshwari V, Shakywanshi R, Khan R, Patel B. Development Of UV Spectroscopic Method Of Dapagliflozin With Some Validation Parameter. *Int J Pharm Sci*. 2025;3(5):42-54.
35. Sanagapati M, Dhanalakshmi K, Reddy GN, Kavitha B. Method Development And Validation Of Dapagliflozin API by UV Spectroscopy. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2014;27(1):270-2.
36. Sumakanth M, Bhavyasri K, Surekha T. Method Development, Validation And Stress Studies Of Dapagliflozin And Metformin Hydrochloride Using Ultraviolet-Visible Spectroscopy In Bulk And Combined Pharmaceutical Formulations. *BiosciBiotechnol Res Commun*. 2020;13(4):1986-92.
37. Ahmad S, Usman MR, Shaikh T, Imran M, Akhtar R. Development and Validation Of UV-Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Saxagliptinand Dapagliflozin in Bulk and Dosage Form. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2021;12(4):2185-92.
38. Mahabole S, Gajeli G, Kalshetti M. RP-HPLC And UV Spectroscopic Method Development And Validation For Estimation Of Dapagliflozin In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form.
39. Antakli S, Kabbani R, Labban R. Analytical Spectrometric Study For Determining Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate Individually OrIn Presence Of Metformin Hydrochloride In Tablets Formulation. *Journal Of Advances In Chemistry*. 2020;17:80-7.
40. Patel D, Dobariya J, Pradhan P, Patel G, Meshram D. Development and Validation of UV spectrophotometric Methods For Simultaneous Estimation Of Lobeglitazone Sulfate And Glimpiride In Combined Dosage Form. *Drug Analytical Research*. 2024 Jul 19;8(1):62-9.
41. Ahamed CS, Sathish M, Sarumathy B, Seenuvasan M, Shuruthiga E, Sharma es. Analytical method developement and validation for estimation of lobeglitazone sulfate in pharmaceutical dosage forms by uv spectrophotometric method.
42. Mudaliar S, Sharma S. Quantification Of LobeglitazoneSulfate In Bulk And Tablet Dosage Form ByA Validated UV Spectroscopy Method: A New Thiazolidinedione Antidiabetic Drug. *Drug MetabBioanal Lett*. 2024;17(2):49-55.
43. Dhara, Patel & Patel, Grishma & Meshram, Dhananjay. (2024). Development And Validation Of UV Spectrophotometric Methods For Simultaneous Estimation Of LobeglitazoneSulfate And Glimpiride In Combined Dosage Form. *Drug Analytical Research*. 8. 62-69. 10.22456/2527-2616.140749.
44. Megha G, Kutty SV, Haribabu Y, Siddharth GJ, Anupama CP, Machado J, Divya V. Novel Validated Approach For the Simultaneous Determination OfLobeglitazoneSulfate and Glimpiride In Its Pure And Combined Dosage Form Using Tandem Quantification Methods By UV-Vis Spectroscopy. *J ApplSpectrosc*. 2025;92:378-387.
45. Kulkarni MM, Khurd SA, Dyade GK, Tupe AP, Jadhav RB. Quantitative Spectrophotometric Estimation OfLobeglitazoneAnd Glimpiride FromThe Combined Formulation By Vierordt's And Q Absorption Technique. *Int J Pharm Pharm Res*. 2025;31(3):493-502.
46. Nithya V, Murugan S, Vetrichelvan T. Stability Indicating Method Development and Validation For the Simultaneous Estimation OfLobeglitazoneSulfateAnd Glimpiride In Bulk And Tablet Dosage By UV Spectrophotometric Method. *Eur J Biomed Pharm Sci*. 2024;11(11):482-5.
47. Khan S, Mahida R. Development And Validation Of UV Spectrophotometric Method Using Area Under Curve ForThe Simultaneous Estimation OfLobeglitazone Sulphate And Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate InA Synthetic Mixture. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2025;14(5):1657-73.

48. Verma MV, Patel CJ, Patel MM. Development And Stability Indicating HPLC Method For Dapagliflozin In API And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *International Journal Of Applied Pharmaceutics*. 2017;9(5):33-41.
49. Manoharan G, Ismaiel AM, Ahmed ZM. Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method Development For Simultaneous Determination And Estimation Of Dapagliflozin In Raw And Tablet Formulation. *Chem Res J*. 2018;3(2):159-64.
50. Deepan T, Dhanaraju MD. Stability Indicating HPLC Method For The Simultaneous Determination Of Dapagliflozin And Saxagliptin In Bulk And Tablet Dosage Form. *Current Issues In Pharmacy And Medical Sciences*. 2018 Apr 11;31(1):39-43.
51. Kommineni V, Chowdary KP, Prasad SV. Development and validation of a new HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of saxagliptine and dapagliflozin and its application in pharmacokinetic studies. *Int Res J Pharm Med Sci*. 2018;1:16-24.
52. Ameenuzzafar, El-Bagory I, Alruwaili NK, Imam SS, Alomar FA, Elkomy MH, Ahmad N, ElmowafyM. Quality by design (QbD) based development and validation of bioanalytical RP-HPLC method for dapagliflozin: Forced degradation and preclinical pharmacokinetic study. *Journal of Liquid Chromatography & Related Technologies*. 2020 Jan 20;43(1-2):53-65.
53. Urooj A, Sundar PS, Vasanthi R, Raja MA, Dutt KR, Rao KN, Ramana H. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and metformin in bulk and in synthetic mixture. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2017 May 20;6(7):2139-50.
54. Sree VN, Bhavyasri DK, Sumakanth DM, Swethasri R. Estimation of Dapagliflozin in Pure and Marketed Formulation by Validated Reverse Phase-High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method.(2020). *Int. J. Life Sci. Pharma Res.*;10(4):P70-84.
55. Deepan T, Rao MB, Dhanaraju MD. Development of validated stability indicating assay method for simultaneous estimation of metformin and dapagliflozin by RP-HPLC. *European Journal of Applied Sciences*. 2017 Jan;9(4):189-99.
56. Begum S, Bhavyasri K, Surekha T, Sumakanth M. RP-HPLC method for dapagliflozin and metformin HCL in bulk and combined formulation. *Archives of Pharmacy Practice*. 2021;12(4-2021):106-10.
57. Mahabole S, Gajeli G, Kalshetti M. RP-HPLC and UV Spectroscopic Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Dapagliflozin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form.
58. Kommineni V, Chowdary KP, Prasad SV. Development of a new stability indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of saxagliptine and dapagliflozin and its validation as per ICH guidelines. *Indo American journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2017 Sep 1;4(09):2920-32.
59. Vankalapati KR, Alegete P, Boodida S. Stability - indicating HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of metformin, dapagliflozin, and saxagliptin in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form. *Biomedical chromatography*. 2022 Jul;36(7):e5384.
60. Sharif S, Bashir R, Adnan A, Mansoor S, Ahmad I, Ch AR, Tahir MS. Stability Indicating, pH and p K a Dependent HPLC–DAD Method for the Simultaneous Determination of Weakly Ionizable Empagliflozin, Dapagliflozin and Canagliflozin in Pharmaceutical Formulations. *Chromatographia*. 2020 Dec;83(12):1453-65.
61. Verma MV, Patel CJ, Patel MM. Development and stability indicating HPLC method for dapagliflozinin API and pharmaceutical dosage form. *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*. 2017;9(5):33-41.
62. Sunkara B, Tummalapalli Naga Venkata GK. Development of novel gradient RP-HPLC method for separation of dapagliflozin and its process-related impurities: insight into stability profile and degradation pathway, identification of degradants using LCMS. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2023 Nov 20;9(1):107.
63. Kant R, Bodla RB, Kapoor G, Bhutani R. Optimization of a single HPLC-PDA method for quantifying metformin, gliclazide, pioglitazone, dapagliflozin,empagliflozin, saxagliptin, linagliptin and teneligliptin using central

- composite design. *Bioorganic chemistry*. 2019 Oct 1;91:103111.
64. Shukla A, Chhalotiya U, Shah D, Tandel J, Kachhiya H, Parmar M. Simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and linagliptin using reverse phase-HPLC with photo diode array (PDA). *Journal of Chemical Metrology*. 2024 Jan 1;18(1).
65. Pathak S, Mishra P. A review on analytical methods of dapagliflozin: An updat. *Int J Pharm QualAssur*. 2020;11(3):355-60.
66. Sura S, Modalavalasa RR, Kothapalli C. Validation of a newly developed stability indicating RP-Liquid Chromatographic Method for the Quantitative Determination of Dapagliflozin. *Der Pharma Chemica*. 2018;10(1):93-102.
67. Hiteksha D, Chotaliya U. Stability indicating RP-HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin Propanediol monohydrate and teneligliptin hydrobromidehydrate in synthetic mixture. *Journal of the Turkish Chemical Society Section A: Chemistry*. 2023;10(4):1025-34.
68. Suma BV, Deveswaran R. An overview on analytical methods for dapagliflozin-an antidiabetic drug. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2019;10(6):2688-92.
69. Mandlik SM, Kawale LA, Wakchaure AA. Simultaneous Estimation of Dapagliflozin and Sitagliptin by RP-HPLC Method Using Quality by Design. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2024 Aug 2;13(18):1061-74.
70. Shirode AR, Khanvilkar VV, Chavan PS, Tamboli GV, Tyagi CK, Chandekar AR. Liquid-Liquid Extraction Assisted Reverse phase HPLC Method for Quantitative Estimation of Dapagliflozin from Biological Matrix-Human Plasma: Development and Validation. *Journal of Neonatal Surgery*. 2025;14(10s).
71. Fattaha HM, Mohamed MA, Mahmouda R, Hassouna ME. Eco-Friendly HPLC Method for Quantification of Metformin and Dapagliflozin in Tablets Dosage Form and Spiking Human Plasma Utilizing Solid Phase Extraction. *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry*. 2024;67(10):307-15.
72. Kashyap T, Honey K, Priyanka V, Mihir J. Novel RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination of dapagliflozin and teneligliptin in tablet formulation and identification of degradation products by LC-MS/MS. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2024 Nov 11;10(1):154.
73. Sravanthi S, Zarin N, Shruthi B, Krishna DR, Manjeera A. A New Analytical Method Development and Validation for the Estimation of Dapagliflozin by Using Reverse Phase-High Performance Liquid Chromatography. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Medical & Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2021;6(4):13-20.
74. Donepudi S, Achanta S. Simultaneous estimation of saxagliptin and dapagliflozin in human plasma by validated high performance liquid chromatography-ultraviolet method. *Turkish Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2019 Mar 27;16(2):227.
75. Zaghary WA, Mowaka S, Hendy MS. Kinetic degradation study of dapagliflozin coupled with UHPLC separation in the presence of major degradation product and metformin. *Chromatographia*. 2019 Apr 1;82(4):777-89.
76. Pal N, Mahtab T, Reddy PP, Rao AS. A New HPLC Method Development and Validation for the Determination of Dapagliflozin in Tablet Dosage Form. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2019 Jun 6;8(9):1156-65.
77. Kavana DC, GS NK. Recent Progress in Analytical Method Development and Validation of Dapagliflozin. *Journal of Pharma Insights and Research*. 2025 Apr 5;3(2):090-7.
78. Bhuma DR, Maddala VK, Raghupathi JK, Salakolusu S, Ranga M, Kaliyapermal M, Katari NK. Acid Degradation Study of Dapagliflozin: Structural Characterization of Dapagliflozin and its Degradation Products Using Advanced Analytical Techniques and In Silico Toxicity Prediction. *Separation Science Plus*. 2025 Jan;8(1):e202400275.
79. Patel YD, Patel PR, Bhatt J, Mehta B, Detholia K. Quantitative computation and stability evaluation of phase III composition comprising sitagliptin and dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate by RP-HPLC. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*. 2022 Jun 5;12(6):148-55.
80. Khagga B, Surekha T, Begum S, Sumakanth M. Development of an RP-HPLC Method for Dapagliflozin and Metformin HCL Analysis.

- Annals of Pharmacy Practice and Pharmacotherapy. 2021;1(1-2021):31-8.
81. Patel B, Teraiya NH. Simultaneous Estimation and Stability Indicating Method of Vildagliptin and Dapagliflozin by Rp-hplc in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *Int Internal Med J.* 2024 Mar 13;2(4):01-6.
82. Kumar RR. Analytical method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and vildagliptin by using RP-HPLC. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2024 Sep 20.
83. Patel NS, Patel BH. Development and Validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method for the Simultaneous Estimation of Dapagliflozin Propanediol and Metformin Hydrochloride in Tablet Dosage Form. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research.* 2020;12(6):660-7.
84. Murugesan AR, Annapurna MM. Simple quantified and validated stability indicating stress degradation studies of oral anti-diabetic agent dapagliflozin by rp-hplc method. *Int. J. App Pharm.* 2022;14(1):231-7.
85. Nandre DS, Ahmed AE, Khan G. Stability indicating HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous Estimation of Dapagliflozin and Metformin tablet dosage form. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2022;15(10):109-4.
86. Kondeti HP, Sankar Dannana G. Development and validation of a stability-indicating rp-hplc method for the estimation of metformin, saxagliptin, and dapagliflozin. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2022;15(3):72-7.
87. Al-Ani I, Al Saadi MT, Alsaadi NT, Al Omari RH, Hamad MF, Dayyih WA, Vicas LG, Awad R. Determination of Canagliflozin, Dapagliflozin, and Empagliflozin in Pharmaceutical Solid Dosage Forms by the HPLC Method. *Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences.* 2024;51(9).
88. Bhamare VB, Bhangale C. ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION AND FORCED DEGRADATION OF DAPAGLIFLOZIN BY RP-HPLC. *WJ of Pha. Res.* 2020 Aug 6;9(12):1006-76.
89. Sen G, Raghu Babu K, Annapurna N, Vekariy NA, Kumar VJ, Pavan Kumar KS, Sharma HK. Validation of stability-indicating reverse phase HPLC method for the determination of related substances in canagliflozin drug substance. *IOSR J. Pharm. Biol. Sci.* 2017;12:86-94.
90. Khagga B, Nandini M, Sowjanya D, Rambabu D, Mogili S. Novel Analytical Method for Combined Dapagliflozin and Vildagliptin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form Using HPLC. *Archives of Pharmacy Practice.* 2024;15(4-2024):5-9.
91. Chaudhary A, Singh BK. Stability-indicating rp-hplc method for simultaneous determination of antidiabetic drugs, dapagliflozin and saxagliptin. *Journal of Advanced Scientific Research.* 2021 Sep 30;12(03 Suppl 1):67-75.
92. Abdel-Gawad SA, AL-TAMIMI AM, Adam EH. Chromatographic Simultaneous Quantification of Dapagliflozin and Metformin Hydrochloride in Presence of their Degradation Products. *Int. J. Biol. Pharm. Allied Sci.* 2017 Oct 6;6(10):2007-21.
93. Vaghela Yavantika V, Patani P, Patel D. Development and validation of stability indicating estimation method of dapagliflozin in it's tablet dosage form. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews.* 2019;6(2):206-13.
94. Mahapatra A, Sreedhar C, Srinivas TR, Akkamma HG, Sunny A, Thakur KP. Analytical method development and statistical validation of dapagliflozin in tablet dosage form and bulk drug. *Indian Research Journal of Pharmacy and Science.* 2018;5(1):1344-56.
95. Shah D, Meshram D, Patel D, Pradhan P, Patel G. Development and validation of green hplc method for simultaneous determination of dapagliflozin and linagliptin in combined dosage form. *Bulletin of Pharmaceutical Sciences Assiut University.* 2024 Dec 1;47(2):1037-48.
96. Sravani K. A validated stability indicating rp-hplc method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin, metformin and saxagliptin in bulk in pharmaceutical oral dosage forms. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2024 Sep 26.
97. Sai KE, Srinivas M, Kumari BU, Sumalatha C, Madhavi A. Development and Validation of an HPLC Method for the Determination of Lobeglitazone in Bulk and in Tablet Formulation. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation.* 2024 Jan 1;14(1).

98. 이종화. Kinetics of the Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion of Lobeglitazone, a Novel Activator of Peroxisome Proliferator-activated Receptor Gamma in Rats (Doctoral dissertation, 서울대학교대학원).
99. Bula Udaya K, Sai KE, Srinivas M, Sumalatha C, Madhavi A. Development and Validation of an HPLC Method for the Determination of Lobeglitazone in Bulk and in Tablet Formulation. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. 2024 Jan 1.
100. Challa GN, Adari J, Kollabathula VP, Yarguntla SR, Koppisetty BR. A Quality by Design Driven RP-HPLC Method for the Assay of Lobeglitazone & Glimepiride and In-silico Admet Studies. *Current Trends in Biotechnology and Pharmacy*. 2025 Jun 10;19(2s):15-29.
101. Priyanka V, Murugan S. Stability indicating method development and validation of Lobeglitazone sulfate by RP-HPLC method. *Int J Pharm Res Appl*. 2024;9(2):853-61.
102. Sulthana R, Bairam R, Yalagatti MS, Prasanthi SV. RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Lobeglitazone sulphate in pharmaceutical dosage form. *GSC Biol Pharm Sci*. 2024;29(2):286-98.
103. Jadav M, Mishra S, Salunkhe M. Method Development and Validation for the Simultaneous Estimation of Lobeglitazone Sulphate and Glimepiride by HPLC Method. *Int J Pharm Qual Assur*. 2024;15(3):1466-73.
104. Buntariya DJ, Mahida R. Reverse phase HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Lobeglitazone sulfate and Glimepiride in pharmaceutical dosage form. *JETIR*. 2024 Aug;11(8): a704-718.
105. Parmar D, Tiwari N, Patani P. Development and validation of stability indicating analytical method for estimation of Lobeglitazone sulphate and Sitagliptin phosphate in a synthetic mixture by HPLC. *Afr J Biomed Res*. 2025 Feb;28(2s):1750-67.
106. Sahu B. Development and validation of stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of lobeglitazone and metformin in tablet dosage form. *Nanotechnol Percept*. 2024;20(S13):101-121.
107. Pustode N, Barsagade A. Method development and validation studies of anti-diabetic drug lobeglitazone from pharmaceutical formulation and human plasma by HPLC-DAD. *Int J Multidiscip Res*. 2024 Sep-Oct;6(5):1-24.
108. Suma BV, Deveswaran R, Premnath SH. A new high-performance thin layer chromatographic method development and validation of dapagliflozin in bulk and tablet dosage form. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2019 Aug 1;11(8):58-63.
109. Shukla A, Chhalotiya U, Shah D, Tandel J, Kachhiya H, Parmar M. Development and validation of stability indicating HPTLC method for simultaneous Estimation of Dapagliflozin and linagliptin. *Discover Chemistry*. 2024 Jun 25;1(1):4.
110. Prajapati P, Patil K, Naik D, Pulusu VS, Haque A, Kalam MA, Shah S. Blue applicability grade index assessment and response surface modelling to synchronous determination of metformin hydrochloride, vildagliptin and dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate by HPTLC method. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2025 Feb 3;11(1):16.
111. Saiyed MI, Shah DA, Chhalotiya U, Tandel JN, Kachhiya HM, Parmar MS, Solanki KH. HPTLC method for determination of anti-hypertensive drug combination metoprolol succinate and dapagliflozin. *Discover Chemistry*. 2024 Sep 2;1(1):13.
112. Desai SA, Mardia RB, Suhagia B, Desai HT. Development and validation of stability-indicating HPTLC method for simultaneous Estimation of metformin, saxagliptin, and Dapagliflozin in their combined matrix using AQB/D. *Bull Env Pharmacol Life Sci*. 2022 Dec 1;12:32-42.
113. Patel AB, Patel PH. Development and validation of HPTLC method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate, sitagliptin phosphate monohydrate and metformin hydrochloride using doe approach. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*. 2025 Jan 1;18(1):309-17.
114. Shah D, Meshram D, Patel D, Pradhan P, Patel G. Development and validation of green hptlc method for simultaneous determination of dapagliflozin and linagliptin in combined dosage form. *Bulletin of Pharmaceutical Sciences Assiut University*. 2024 Dec 1;47(2):1037-48.
115. Patel KP, Chhalotiya UK, Shah DA, Kachhiya HM, Tandel JN, Parmar MS, Solanki KH, Vaghasiya J. Stability indicating densitometric

- analysis for simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate and Telmisartan. *Essential Chem.* 2025 Dec 31;2(1):2495035.
116. Prajapati P, Kapupara P, Vekariya H. Development, and validation of HPTLC method for simultaneous quantification of dapagliflozin and vildagliptin in tablet dosage form. *J Chem Health Risks.* 2023;13(6):3643-9.
117. Karmankar SR, Tajne MR. A validated stability indicating high performance thin layered chromatographic method for the analysis of dapagliflozin in bulk drug and marketed tablet formulation. *Asian J Chem.* 2019;31(7):1457-60.
118. Chaudhari P, Patil P, Shah C, Upadhyay U. Review of chromatographic and spectrophotometric methods for dapagliflozin estimation in bulk and formulations. *Journal of Dynamics and Control.* 2024;8(10):67-88.
119. Kalsara K, Tadvi N, Upadhyay U. Development and validation of UV spectroscopic and HPTLC methods for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and metoprolol in synthetic mixture. *Int J Res Dev Pharm L Sci.* 2024 Jul 13.
120. Ahmed HM, Omar MA, Batakoushy HA, Abdel Hamid MAA. HPTLC-densitometric analysis of selected antidiabetic drugs in presence of their degradation products. *Microchemical Journal.* 2020;154:104560
121. Sen DB, Baldha K, Sen AK, Maheshwari RA, Zanwar AS, KP G, Pradhan PK. Synchronized Assessment of Lobeglitazone Sulfate and Metformin Hydrochloride in Tablet by Robust, High-performance Thin-layer Chromatographic Method. *Current Pharmaceutical Analysis.* 2024 Jun;20(5):345-57.
122. Sen AK, Sarkar T, Sen DB, Maheshwari RA, Zanwar AS, Dumpala RL. Quantitative determination of lobeglitazone sulfate and glimepiride in combined tablet by robust high - performance thin layer chromatographic method. *Separation Science Plus.* 2024 Jul;7(7):e202400059.
123. Ismail A, Haroun M, Alahmad Y. Qualitative and Quantitative Determination of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate and Its Related Substances and Degradation Products Using LC-MS and Preparative Chromatography Methods. *Baghdad Science Journal.* 2023 Oct 28;20(5 (Suppl.)).
124. Goday S, Shaik AR, Avula P. Development and validation of a LC-ESI-MS/MS based bioanalytical method for dapagliflozin and saxagliptin in human plasma. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research.* 2018 Oct 1;52(4):S277-86.
125. Ngo QT, Le DC. Development and validation of a LC-MS/MS method for quantification of dapagliflozin in human plasma. *Tạp chí Nghiên cứu Dược và Thông tin Thuốc.* 2024 Jun 29;17:28-35.
126. Kalyan S, Parle A. A validated LC-MS/MS method for simultaneous Estimation of Dapagliflozin and Metformin in pharmaceutical dosage form. *IOSR J Pharm.* 2020;10(11):31-8.
127. He X, Li Y, Ma Y, Fu Y, Xun X, Cui Y, Dong Z. Development of UPLC-MS/MS method to study the pharmacokinetic interaction between sorafenib and dapagliflozin in rats. *Molecules.* 2022 Sep 21;27(19):6190.
128. Üner B. An LC-MS/MS method development for dapagliflozin-loaded nanostructured lipid carrier formulation in rabbit plasma. *Journal of Research in Pharmacy.* 2024 Mar 1;28(2):438-46.
129. Kommineni V, Gupta JK, Panigrahy UP, Deepthi KL, Krishnan K, Chandan R. Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry Assay Method for Estimation of Saxagliptine and Dapagliflozin in Human Plasma. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results.* 2022 Oct 9;13(8):2123-31.
130. Kim HJ, Lee JH, Park JS, Park JJ, Lee HW, Bunch H, Seong SJ, Gwon MR, Yoon YR. LC-MS-Based Untargeted Metabolic Profiling in Plasma Following Dapagliflozin Administration in Healthy Volunteers. *Metabolites.* 2025 Jul 17;15(7):484.
131. Phanindra AD, Kumar YS. Development and validation of sensitive LC-ESI-MS/MS method for the simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and saxagliptin in human plasma. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2019;11:55-9
132. Suma BV, Deveswaran R. An overview on analytical methods for dapagliflozin-an antidiabetic drug. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2019;10(6):2688-92.

133. Rathod SM, Aakhunji CM, Patel NC. Development and validation of lc-ms/ms method for detection and characterisation of forced degradation products of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate and vildagliptin: greenness assessment using agree.
134. Shah PA, Shrivastav PS, Shah JV, George A. Simultaneous quantitation of metformin and dapagliflozin in human plasma by LC–MS/MS: application to a pharmacokinetic study. *Biomedical Chromatography*. 2019 Apr;33(4):e4453.
135. Chan-Jiang E, Godoy R, Mennickent S, Vergara C, de Diego M. Determination of the Chemical Stability of Dapagliflozin by LC/DAD and MS/MS Methods. *Journal of Chromatographic Science*. 2022 Sep;60(8):741-9.
136. Surendran S, Paul D, Pokharkar S, Deshpande A, Giri S. A LC-MS/MS method for simultaneous estimation of a novel anti-diabetic combination of saxagliptin and dapagliflozin using a polarity switch approach: application to in vivo rat pharmacokinetic study. *Analytical Methods*. 2019;11(2):219-26.
137. Aubry AF, Gu H, Magnier R, Morgan L, Xu X, Tirmenstein M, Wang B, Deng Y, Cai J, Couerbe P, Arnold M. Validated LC–MS/MS methods for the determination of dapagliflozin, a sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitor in normal and ZDF rat plasma. *Bioanalysis*. 2010 Dec 1;2(12):2001-9.
138. Liu Z, Liu Y, Wang Z, Lu H, Zhu X, Bao Y, Cai B, Gao S, Tao X, Xu D. A Simple and Sensitive LC–MS/MS Method for Determination of Dapagliflozin and Its Major Metabolite in Human Plasma. *Journal of Chromatographic Science*. 2025 Apr;63(4):bmaf019.
139. Gu A, Zhang C, Li D, Cen B, Cao W, Xu Z. A Simple, Sensitive, and Stable LC–MS/MS Method for the Simultaneous Determination and Pharmacokinetic Study of Dapagliflozin and Its Metabolite D3OG in Human Plasma. *Biomedical Chromatography*. 2025 Jun;39(6):e70108.
140. Prajapati A, Kevat H, Maheriya B, Joshi H, Vadalia J, Dudhatra B, Thummar K. Novel Stability-Indicating Assay for Concurrent Quantification of Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin Via Rp-Hplc and Lc-Ms/Ms Analysis of Degradation Products. *Ms Analysis of Degradation Products*. 2024.
141. DAS T, KRISHNAN NJ, JOHN AR. Concurrent Bio-Analysis and Validation of Empagliflozin, Dapagliflozin, Metformin and Linagliptin in Spiked Human Blood Plasma By RPLCMS/MS. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (09752366)*. 2021 Apr 1;13(2).
142. Arbouche N, Blanchot A, Raul JS, Kintz P. First identification of dapagliflozin in human hair: Development of a new liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry method. *Drug Testing and Analysis*. 2023 Sep;15(9):987-93.
143. Valiya G, Kachhiya H, Sutarsandhiya R, Patel R, Tandel J, Chhalotiya U, et al. Accelerated Stability Indicating LC Method for Simultaneous Quantification of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate and Bisoprolol Fumarate. *Separation Science Plus*. 2025 Jun;8(6).
144. Kim B, Shin HS, Kim JR, Lim KS, Yoon SH, Yu KS, Shin SG, Jang IJ, Cho JY. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of CKD-501, lobeglitazone, in human plasma and urine using LC–MS/MS and its application to a pharmacokinetic study. *Chromatographia*. 2012 Jun;75(11):671-7.
145. Lee JH, Woo YA, Hwang IC, Kim CY, Kim DD, Shim CK, Chung SJ. Quantification of CKD-501, lobeglitazone, in rat plasma using a liquid-chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry method and its applications to pharmacokinetic studies. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*. 2009 Dec 5;50(5):872-7.
146. Lee JH, Ahn SH, Maeng HJ, Lee W, Kim DD, Chung SJ. The identification of lobeglitazone metabolites in rat liver microsomes and the kinetics of the in vivo formation of the major metabolite M1 in rats. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*. 2015 Nov 10;115:375-82.
147. Moon SJ, Yu KS, Kim MG. An assessment of pharmacokinetic interaction between lobeglitazone and sitagliptin after multiple oral administrations in healthy men. *Clinical therapeutics*. 2020 Jun 1;42(6):1047-57.
148. Kim JW, Kim JR, Yi S, Shin KH, Shin HS, Yoon SH, Cho JY, Kim DH, Shin SG, Jang IJ, Yu KS. Tolerability and pharmacokinetics of lobeglitazone (CKD-501), a peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ agonist: a single-

- and multiple-dose, double-blind, randomized control study in healthy male Korean subjects. *Clinical therapeutics*. 2011 Nov 1;33(11):1819-30.
149. Shin D, Kim TE, Yoon SH, Cho JY, Shin SG, Jang IJ, Yu KS. Assessment of the pharmacokinetics of co-administered metformin and lobeglitazone, a thiazolidinedione antihyperglycemic agent, in healthy subjects. *Current Medical Research and Opinion*. 2012 Jul 1;28(7):1213-20.
150. Kumar CV, Aparna P, Kumar YR, Reddy GR. Determination of residual solvents in dapagliflozin amorphous by gas chromatography with static head space method. *Der. Pharmacia. Lettre*. 2016;8(9):349-56.
151. Barreto J, Borges C, Rodrigues TB, Jesus DC, Campos-Staffico AM, Nadruz W, da Costa JL, de Oliveira RB, Sposito AC. Pharmacokinetic properties of dapagliflozin in hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis patients. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 2023 Aug 1;18(8):1051-8.

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